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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“BITTERSWEET”

Memories to ponder in the past;
Time flies by so fast,
A sense of fondness came;
A nostalgia struck their names.

Why depart so early?
Two brothers dearest to me,
On Earth they were treated unpleasantly;
In heaven they are free.

Moments incomplete;
If only minutes, hours repeat,
Say the words unsaid;
All negative acts were corrected.

Am I to be happy or gloomy?
Absence of them is melancholy;
No, it cannot be,
Faith is the key;
Lord God, please keep them by your side;
You alone, Almighty God will be their soul's guide.